

Notes

Schiff Base Complexes of Titanium(III)

S. F. H. RIZVI & NASEER AHMAD

Department of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh

Manuscript received 11 December 1974; revised 28 January 1976;
accepted 7 June 1976

THE present day chemical literature records only a few Schiff base complexes of titanium(IV)^{1,2} and had only one with titanium(III)³. We have recently reported eight new complexes of titanium(III) with Schiff bases⁴. The present communication deals with the synthesis, isolation and characterization—by elemental analyses, m.p.s, thermogravimetric analysis, molar conductance, infra red spectra and magnetic moments—of titanium(III) complexes with the Schiff bases of (a) 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde with ethylene diamine, *o*-phenylene diamine, dianisidine, benzidine, (b) 4-chlorobenzaldehyde with benzidine, dianisidine, *o*-phenylene diamine and (c) 2-methoxybenzaldehyde with *o*-phenylene diamine.

Experimental

Dianisidine, ethylene diamine, *o*-phenylene diamine and 2-methoxy benzaldehyde were reagent grade and used as such. $TiCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ was synthesised⁵, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde and 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde were recrystallised and 2-methoxybenzaldehyde was distilled before use.

The aldehyde and amine were taken in the molar ratio of 2 : 1 in ethanol, stirred for 2-4 hr and the resulting precipitate separated and washed with ethanol and recrystallised out. The purity of the ligands was ascertained by their elemental analysis for C, H and N.

The titanium(III) chloride was allowed to react with Schiff bases in the stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 1 with a slight excess of the Schiff bases in dry tetrahydrofuran. The precipitate was separated, washed with the same solvent and dried *in vacuo*. The whole of the work of synthesis was carried out in a dry inert glove bag because titanium(III) is susceptible to oxidation by air and prone to hydrolysis by moisture and the resulting complex is apt to decomposition and oxidation with air. The elemental analyses were done at this Department and at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. A known amount of the complex was fused with pure caustic potash in a platinum crucible, dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the chloride estimated as silver chloride.

Conductance was measured in DMSO with a Philips conductivity bridge model PR-9500 in conjunction with a dip type cell. The magnetic moments were determined by Gouy method and the diamagnetic correction for the ligands was applied. Thermograms were taken at the BARC, Bombay with a Bausch and Lomb thermogravimetric balance, at a heating rate of 6° per minute between room temperature and 520° in an inert atmosphere. The i.r. spectra of the complexes and the ligands were taken in KBr phase on a Perkin Elmer infra red spectrophotometer model 621.

Results and Discussion

Chemical analyses give the formulae for the complexes as given in the Table. Some of the hydrogen analyses are quite high because the complexes readily absorb moisture when exposed to air during micro-analyses.

The magnetic moment of these complexes after applying diamagnetic correction for the ligands lie in the range of 1.44 to 1.75 B.M., showing that the metal is in the trivalent state. The values lower than 1.73 B.M. might be due to the slight oxidation of the complexes. The same has been observed in the titanium(III) *o*-phenanthroline complex⁶.

The molar conductances of these complexes are between 25.2 and 70.6 mhos per mole cm^2 in dimethylsulphoxide. This range is quite compatible with 1 : 1 electrolytes⁷⁻⁸. It suggests that, in all these complexes, one out of three chlorides is outside the coordination sphere and the remaining two are coordinated to the metal.

The high temperatures (see Table) at which the two water molecules in the complexes of bis(4-hydroxybenzaldehyde)dianisidine, bis(4-hydroxybenzaldehyde)benzidine and bis(4-chlorobenzaldehyde)dianisidine, are eliminated as shown by TGA, proves that the two water molecules in these complexes are inside the coordination sphere. The tetrahydrofuran molecule present in bis(4-chlorobenzaldehyde)benzidine and bis(2-methoxybenzaldehyde) *o*-phenylene diamine complexes is removed respectively, at 228° and 230°, which prove that it is coordinated with the metal ion.

In i.r. the most important absorption is that of the CN stretching. Biradar and Kulkarni⁹ reported that CN stretching occurs at 1625-30 cm^{-1} and is shifted to higher frequency, i.e., 1630-1650 cm^{-1} on complexation. This absorption occurs at 1635(s), 1619(s), 1650(s), 1620(s), 1625(s), 1620(m), 1602(s)

NOTES

TABLE—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES AND OTHER CHARACTERISING DATA.

Complex	Elemental Analyses%				Colour	Magnetic moment B.M.	Λ_M $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{mole}^{-1}$	Removal of water or tetrahydrofuran (% loss at temperature)		
	C	H	N	Cl				1H ₂ O	2H ₂ O	1 THF
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1. [(C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-OH Benz)en Ti(III)]Cl	(41.90) 42.22	(6.16) 5.99	(6.63) 5.98	(18.65) 18.91	yellow	1.75	*	—	—	—
2. [(C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-OH Benz) o-phen Ti(III)]Cl	(51.46) 51.14	(3.40) 3.44	(5.95) 5.86	(34.93) 33.90	dirty white	1.44	68.8	—	—	—
3. [(C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₅)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl H ₂ O [Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O.bis(4-OH Benz)dian. Ti(III)]Cl.H ₂ O	(53.40) 53.52	(5.30) 5.53	(4.23) 4.39	(26.74) 26.56	yellow	*	22.7	68°C (2.54) 2.35	128°C (8.61) 8.51	—
4. [(C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃)Cl ₂ Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O.bis(4-OH Benz)Bn. Ti(III)]Cl	(48.45) 47.92	(4.78) 5.21	(4.82) 4.91	(16.10) 16.21	light yellow	1.48	29.7	—	180°C (5.99) 5.28	—
5. [(C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ OCl ₄)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-Cl-Benz)Bn.THF. Ti(III)]Cl	(55.43) 55.08	(3.56) 4.63	(4.52) 4.58	(28.59) 27.40	dirty white	*	70.3	—	—	228°C (14.90) 14.30
6. [(C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₃ .Cl ₄)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ 2H ₂ O.bis(4-Cl Benz)dian. Ti(III)]Cl	(48.01) 48.03	(3.83) 4.01	(4.11) 4.08	(26.81) 26.04	brown	1.52	68.8	—	150°C (5.88) 6.00	—
7. [(C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ Cl ₄)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(4-Cl-Benz)o-phen Ti(III)]Cl	(49.41) 50.02	(3.16) 3.86	(5.52) 5.49	(25.12) 24.90	dirty white	1.47	69.9	—	—	—
8. [(C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂)Ti]Cl [Cl ₂ bis(2-MeO Benz)o-phen. THF Ti(III)]Cl	(54.70) 54.68	(4.91) 4.39	(4.90) 4.91	(18.26) 17.90	dirty white	1.44	25.2	—	—	230°C (13.46) 13.40

* amount insufficient

Theoretical percentages are given in parentheses

THF = tetrahydrofuran; en = ethylene diamine; o-phen = orthophenylene diamine; dian = dianisidine; Benz = benzaldehyde; Bn = benzidine; MeO = methoxy.

and 1626(s) in these ligands and is in most cases shifted to higher frequency on complexation, i.e., 1651(s), 1650(s), 1645(s), 1650(s), 1650(m), 1620(s), 1639(s) and 1645(s) cm^{-1} respectively in the complexes arranged in the Table. In the complexes containing phenolic OH group there is no change in the i.r. spectra of the complexes in the region of OH deformation, that is 1200 cm^{-1} , and 1410–1310 cm^{-1} . Hence it is concluded that coordination occurs through nitrogen and not through phenolic hydroxyl groups.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. W. Rahman, Head, for providing research facilities and to the management of Shia Degree College, Lucknow for granting leave to S.F.H.R.

References

1. YA YU CHUANG, I. A. SAVICH, A. V. LAPITSKI, V. R. SAM and L. G. TIPOV-VESTNIK, *Moskov Univ.*, ser. 11, 15, 1960, No. 3, 40.
2. V. A. KOGAN, O. A. OSIPOV, V. I. MINKIN and V. P. SOKOLOV, *Neorgan. Khim., Zh.*, 1965, 10, 83; *Chem. Abs.*, 61, 10174f.
3. B. R. SINGH and S. KUMAR, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 663.

4. S. F. H. RIZVI and NASEER AHMAD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 1084.
5. N. AHMAD, S. M. F. RAHMAN and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 515.
6. M. M. KHAN and N. AHMAD, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1967, 40, 1254.
7. P. G. SEARS, G. R. LESTER and L. R. DAWSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 1433.
8. N. N. GREENWOOD, B. P. STRONGHAN and A. E. WILSON, *J. Chem. Soc., (A)*, 1968, 2209.
9. N. S. BIRADAR and V. H. KULKARNI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, 33, 3847.

Thermodynamic Ionization Constant of Salicyloylhydrazide in Aqueous Solution

R. K. BHATNAGAR, U. S. GUPTA & K. K. PANDE*

Chemical Laboratories, Government Science College, Gwalior

Manuscript received 17 March 1975; revised 24 May 1976; accepted 28 May 1976

MEAUREMENTS of the extent of ionization were previously made by the method of visual colorimetry by Hammett and coworkers¹ and also

* Head, Chemistry Department, Govt. Science College, Gwalior.